

“The Era Of Mobile Applications In Digital Marketing Innovation”

OPEN ACCESS

Volume : 7

Special Issue : 3

Month : February

Year: 2019

ISSN: 2320-4168

Impact Factor: 4.118

Citation:

Sitrarasu, S. “The Era of Mobile Applications in Digital Marketing Innovation.” *Shanlax International Journal of Commerce*, vol. 7, no. S3, 2019, pp. 75–84.

DOI:

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.2572432>

Dr.S.Sitrarasu

*Associate Professor of Commerce, Dr.G.R.Damodaran College of Science
Avinashi Road, Coimbatore, Tamil Nadu*

Abstract

Today's time of Internet has opened the gateway of tremendous digital marketing opportunities for businesses. By utilizing different channels of digital marketing, businesses cannot just share their product and services online; additionally they can gain clients for their business, entice them and can convert them to boost their ROI. The speed and straightforwardness with which the digital media transmits data and support a business is astonishing. The world is super-connected nowadays and all things considered, marketing and advertising are no more the same as they once were. This is particularly valid because of the ascent of online networking, which has changed how organizations speak with potential and existing customers. Digital Marketing is an aggregate term, which is utilized where advertising and marketing meet web innovation and different types of online media platforms. This paper deals with the contribution of mobile applications for the recent innovation in Digital marketing revolution.

Keywords: Customer Satisfaction, Digital Marketing, Innovation, Marketing and Mobile apps.

Introduction

Digital Marketing can be understood as a well-targeted, conversion-oriented, quantifiable, and interactive marketing of products or services by utilizing digital innovation to achieve the customers, and transform them into clients in a sustainable fashion. The whole concept and functionalities of Digital Marketing are more competent, effective, result-oriented and measurable, which make it very different from traditional marketing.

The traditional way of marketing lets businesses market their products or administrations on print media, radio and TV commercials, bill boards, business cards, and in numerous other comparable ways where Internet or web-based social networking sites were not utilized for promoting. However, traditional promoting approaches had constrained client reachability and extent of driving clients' purchasing conduct. In addition, traditional marketing methods were not quantifiable too.

Digital Marketing

1. Communication is bidirectional in Digital Marketing as businesses can communicate with customers and customers can ask queries or make suggestions to businesses as well.

2. Medium of communication is more powerful and involves social media websites, chats, apps and Email.
3. Digital marketing campaigns can be developed quite rapidly and with digital tools, channelizing Digital Marketing campaigns is easier.
4. It is very effective for reaching global audiences.
5. Digital Marketing lets you measure the effectiveness of a digital marketing campaign through analytics.
6. Digital Marketing accomplishes targets of marketing of a business through various Digital Marketing Channels.

Mobile App Marketing Strategy

Growing prevalence of smart-phones makes mobile app one of the most important parts of 'digital marketing PDF'. While building your mobile App, below given are the important things you need to pay heed upon-

- You need to optimize social media presence of your App by improving a steady social media following on different social networks like Facebook, Google+, Twitter, Instagram, Tumblr, etc.
- You should drive engagement across your mobile app by focusing your efforts on boosting ongoing engagement and keep updating fresh content to influence users have interest in your app.
- Another important factor is to increasing app store ratings that you ought to try, as this will drive a lot of traffic to your app.
- Ensuring a steady rise in app downloads is one of the important things you need to consider in mobile marketing. However, if your product is valuable, its download rate will automatically increase.

Marketing Apps

There are many types of apps that you could use your marketing advantage, whether these are mobile apps or on-site web apps. Each type has a strength to play, and choosing which to focus on is a matter of preference on what you want to achieve for your brand.

Web apps can turn a static web page into something more functional and interactive that better engages users and can help to convert users into leads. On the other hand, if your firm invests heavily in content marketing, produces content frequently, and has a loyal audience, a mobile app can be a great way to deliver content into the hands of your audience.

All in all, it's a diverse marketing strategy that can be used in multiple ways. Other B2B firms are creating apps for tradeshows, events, and networking. For more product-oriented B2B firms, apps can be used for sales as well.

How are mobile apps helpful?

Even though we are aware of the fact that digital marketing is constantly evolving with technological advancements, mobile apps are working as a game changer in the whole scenario. With the evolution of smartphones and tablets, mobile apps influenced the lives of thousands of people, including yours and mine. Mobile apps have not only made life easier but helped us in business building. Sending emails, online information search, online purchases and client connections were never so easy, before the concept of the mobile app.

According to a survey conducted by Fierce Developer, mobile apps and smartphones have unknowingly influenced human behaviour. On an average, more than 50% of the time by mobile users is spent on apps.

Just like online lifestyle company Myntra, many eCommerce sites are planning to shift their desktop and mobile site to an app-only eCommerce platform. The reason is quite simple, as per a survey, Myntra found that 85% of online users were using native mobile apps instead of mobile sites. Many other online companies have realized the power of mobile apps and are planning to move their online business to mobile apps.

Along the app revolution, your smartphone will automatically take you to the native app when you click on any available product link, or it will give you the downloadable link to the App store. More than 1.5 million live apps on App Store and Play Store, if you want better digital marketing results you need to introduce a relevant app to your customers, for greater user experience. Digital marketers understand the growing trend and have resorted to offering relevant app development and marketing services to clients.

Some interesting statistics about mobile apps

With mobile app revenue expected to touch the scale of \$189 billion by the year 2020, here are some interesting and unbelievable facts about mobile apps:

- 90% of mobile users spend their time in apps as compared to mobile sites, according to data by Flurry 2015.
- According to a survey conducted in May 2016, the average cost per app installation is \$2.33 for Android and \$1.46 for iOS.
- Approximately 26% apps are abandoned by the users after their first use, and 25% of apps are never used after installation, as per 2015 data by Google.
- As per Adobe Mobile Maturity Survey of 2015, approximately 78% of organisations use paid media to divert traffic towards app downloads.
- If you compare customer satisfaction, 47% users dislike their website experience, whereas 45% of app users dislike their app experience.

How can a mobile app help to increase your revenue?

Here are some of the best tips from top app company CEOs and app marketers for financial growth:

- 1 Amir Jirbandey, from Dubber, believes in revenue increase with the growth in user signups. He says, “Increase in user numbers naturally results in revenue growth for us. However, by increasing the usage of each user, we can see a growing ARPU.”
- 2 Dakota Smith from Hopper, dedicates her app success to the methods of refining and polishing your push-notification strategy, which can become the key for converting your install base into your paying customers.
- 3 Washos, app by Benjamin Guez, became popular and excelled in its revenue growth vis quality service delivery and email marketing. They believe that their success in growing sales is connected profusely to their capacity to deliver best in class service.

As much as it is important to realise that your business needs to stay on the top, it is crucial to know how to do it and by what means. In the digital sea full of billions of apps, it is good to know which tool helps the most. As a digital marketer, you need to enhance your speciality in multiple segments.

The top five useful mobile apps for digital marketers are Evernote to organize everything, HootSuite for Social Media Management, Flipboard for inspiration, Redbooth for collaboration and Google Apps for all other work related needs.

The facts and tactics mentioned above are the highlights on how mobile apps are changing the face of digital marketing. Whether you are new to the digital world or a digital marketing pro,

switching over to mobile app will be highly beneficial for you. As a marketer, you may have various methods of attracting customers, but a tie up between app and business is the need of the hour.

Mobile Apps Changing the Face of Digital Marketing

Who would have thought that in 2017 we are able to do so much on our mobiles? Literally from the palm of our hands, we can browse catalogs, purchase products and so very much more. This has led mobile usage to balloon up to an astounding eight hours a day – quite literally half our waking hours. Because people are using their mobiles more than desktops, brands and companies have adapted and now meet users where they spend most of their time, on social media.

It's safe to say that people are using technology more than they care to spend on sleeping. Mobile apps are therefore competing to engage and hold the attention of users for longer periods, while including features that are beneficial for companies and brands.

The role of apps

Apps are the launch pad for companies and brands onto mobile devices, allowing for the creation of an immersive user experience and a platform for engagement.

Within mobile apps you'll find a range of features that better the user's experience, particularly with social media apps. A great example, the Canvas feature on Facebook allows companies and brands to beautifully tell stories and showcase their products and services.

The benefits of such app features? For one, users need not exit an app to engage with a company or a brand. Instead, the wheels have turned and now brands and companies are going the extra mile to meet their consumers and prospective customers. These features have created an avenue for companies and brands to target their intended audience much more accurately.

Before the practice of digital marketing, traditional advertisers had little control of accurately knowing who, where and how far the reach of their message has gone.

With the targeting capabilities and the almost endless possibilities of digital marketing on mobile apps, paid media strategists of digital marketing agencies are able to produce the right content and ensure that it reaches the right people, at the right time.

Let's delve into the details of targeting and engaging on mobile apps as it's more than just the features, accessibility, and linking between mobile users and companies. For one, companies and brands can have a great reach with programmatic media.

Programmatic Media

Programmatic media is software based, automated buying of media. Programmatic media includes display, video, social, radio, television and other media. Digital marketers can use programmatic media for its insights and use the data gathered to tweak creative across an entire campaign. What's more, programmatic media provides valuable information that can be used to better future targeting, and so aim to paint a complete picture.

The use of programmatic media is definitely a great strategy for one-to-one marketing. Programmatic media provides companies and brands with the guidance of intelligent data that can be used to offer the mobile user with a well-integrated, seamless experience within their app of choice. No longer do mobile users need to hop from app to app to complete an action, as software such as programmatic media allows companies and brands to go all the way and meet users where they are at the right time.

This software taps into targeting campaign parameters. Its qualitative form affords paid media to serve relevant ads to the right person. This demonstrates the impact of programmatic media

and how it strengthens targeting. This kind of marketing allows paid media teams to deliver their message when the prospects are thinking about it.

Mobiles have changed the face of digital marketing. The features of social media, combined with programmatic media, strengthens the connection between the customer and brand. Of course, there are many other features that contribute to the way digital marketing is done. We can only expect more innovative features and tools to push the boundaries of how we market on social media and apps.

Mobile apps have gone from being a launch pad to the primary, go-to channel for consumers to connect with their favourite brands and companies. With the benefits comes challenges too. For digital marketers, they have to cross unfamiliar channels as well as targeting problems. To conquer and succeed, it requires attention to detail and A/B testing to reach the desired audience and the right time.

Mobile Apps and How They Make Your Digital Marketing Different

What makes mobile apps a smart choice for business? Well, it's all about the pocket end-to-end user experience that makes it easier for businesses to engage and retain their customer interest.

While your competitors might try improving the website experience, strengthen technology infrastructure and try complimenting their service with cutting edge technologies, you can do many of these with just one mobile application.

And Mobile App Marketing Goes Beyond

Some interesting facts to consider about mobile apps include:

- 50 percent of all ecommerce transactions happen through mobile devices
- 85 percent of customers prefer using a mobile application instead of a mobile website
- Mobile apps will be a key enabler in driving brand recognition
- More and more business investors are including hybrid mobile app in their marketing campaign. One such example is that of the RFID or the beacon integrated app.
- Wearable devices have become an important part of peoples' lives and so are the apps integrated in them.

Digital Marketing is No Longer About Being Just Responsive

In other words, your mobile app marketing should be anything but conventional. All these above facts help us to determine one thing about the future of digital market. Everything is going to be mobile and it's time for businesses to gear up for this. You might be wondering whether or not this would be a good option going for. I would say, very soon you will find yourself eventually going down this path and here's why.

Reasons Why Mobile Apps Are Important For Your Business

1 – All Time Visibility

According to market statistics, Americans spend more than two hours a day on their mobile devices.

While it's true that there are few apps out there that enjoy full-time visibility. If your app is relevant and provides a useful function to engage with your company, it will probably be used beyond the initial download.

2 – Direct Marketing Channel

There are two things that make having a mobile app a worthwhile marketing asset. First, it gives you the chance to be with your target audience at all times

Second, providing business marketers a direct means of interaction with the customers.

With the push notification feature, marketers can now be one-step closer to ringing the door bell of a customer. Not only can they inform customers about any new arrivals, but also send them reminders about any product or service whenever it's appropriate.

3 – Innovative Approaches

Whether you are running a spa service or selling flowers, your existing customers will reach out to you at some point. By including a mobile app in your marketing and communication mix can make it that much easier for them.

By accessing your app, customers can find out product or service time availability without having to call. making things more convenient for them and less troublesome for you.

4 – Customer Loyalty Value

The power of a mobile app can be a great means of building customer value, and there are many ways you can do it. For example – providing customers an opportunity to review their rewards/ points via mobile app or helping customers locate a nearby retail store where they are likely to find a product they are looking for.

There are many ways to buildup a long-term customer loyalty value. And building that loyalty value will help you to find more return customers.

5 – Respond Better

Mobile apps have made it easier for businesses to respond to their customer problems faster and more effectively.

They can keep track of rising customer demand and also access customer information.

Standing out in the crowd is one of the biggest challenges faced by marketers today. Investing in a mobile marketing tool like an app can help you overcome this problem in many ways. While this may be true there are many out there who might be confused about what features to include in their mobile app development.

Here are some tips that you would like to go through therefore –

Customize Your App Design

Some of the things that a user looks for when they download an app are – personalization, seamless navigation and hassle-free experience.

Make sure that your mobile app includes all the key customization features in order to align with the customer needs and preferences. Design your mobile app to make it engaging, interactive and to build a strong brand relationship with customers.

Simple Navigational System

A couple of vital things that you need to keep in mind are – the content and the screen size.

Make sure that the content and the design do not end up cramming up the entire mobile space. When you are designing a mobile app, make sure that you design it to ensure seamless navigation and impressive product display.

You can implement a responsive design – a solution that's tailored to fit any screen size and resolution and helps to render an immersive experience.

Simple Registration Process

Lengthy registration processes are a big turn off when it comes to mobile apps. The rule of thumb is to make registration as simple as possible, for example – allow your customers can sign up using an email id and a mobile number.

During the time of checkout, many apps provide users with the option to save their information for future use. This is a very important feature to get people through the entire conversion funnel.

Smart Analytics

Smart analytics is an important feature that your mobile app should include, and that's because your core objective is to generate revenue. With analytics, you can evaluate and understand your users' behavior and their buying pattern.

There are many things that smart analytics can help you with when it comes to evaluating success. Some of these are –

- The cost of conversion
- The session time
- The custom field access
- Click-through rate
- Leading customer behavior
- Higher revenue streams

Discussion about the Topic

“Creating and retaining the customer is Marketing” says the modern definition. The marketers today are very innovative and creative in their marketing approach. They want to make a successful combination of the marketing mixes. The innovative or creative ideas have to be implemented in any of the four mixes of marketing called Product, Price, Place and Promotion. When the competition is acute in the market, every business is striving for their survival and growth. But at the same time some start-up businesses proved to be successful. So what makes success for some businesses and struggle for other businesses is the question of mystery. If we analyse the success stories of the businesses, we can understand that the successful and profitable start-ups have rightly identified the business gaps and attempted to deliver the same at the ease of consumers with the help of available modern technologies. The picture of ‘Marketing’ including its definition has been changing drastically and constantly. But one thing remains common at all the time is “Marketing revolves around the need or want satisfaction of customers”. To conclude the discussion, the businesses who appropriately identify the need and want of the consumers and make right combination of marketing mixes to satisfy and enthuse the customer with the help of new technology can be successful in their marketing effort.

Let me take fewer successful examples for further discussion

1. Food Delivery Apps

One of the fastest growing and most successful start-up businesses is the food delivery app. Food is the basic need of human. For a long time, food items were sold offline i.e. in restaurant itself. Slowly the restaurants started extending the parcel services to benefit the customers. At a later time when the usage of phones and mobile phones were increasing, the restaurants were providing the phone call based parcel service. Just within a period of a decade the use of smartphone with internet service has reached most of the Indian consumers. Mobile applications are developed for all human needs. Mobile apps are faster, easier and connected to the GPS system. Hence, it is much easier now to locate the consumers for delivering the product or services.

The Food delivery apps which emerged during 2013, contain details of all food items and price list. They receive orders from customers through mobile application and process orders to appropriate restaurants, pick up the parcel from restaurants and deliver food items to the place of consumers' choice. The convenience to the consumers is that they can get the food of the restaurant

even if they don't have delivery services and with the help of the smart phone with GPS system the parcel can be delivered to consumers wherever they are. The result of a research reveals that 25% of smartphone users have at least one food delivery app in their smart phone. Top ten most popular food delivery app in India are Swiggy, Zomato Order, Uber Eats, Foodpanda, Domino's, Pizza Hut, JustEat, Faaso's, TastyKhana and FoodMingo.

2. Mobile App based Taxi/Auto

Yet another successful model of e-business which is more successful today is the mobile app based taxi or auto services. Unlike the food delivery app, a separate mobile application is required for every service provider. A customer can avail the service of taxi or auto on the go from anywhere to any part of the city. The customers have to first check the availability of the taxi or auto for their location through mobile application, then fix the destination they want to reach and then confirm the booking after verifying the probable fare. The taxi/auto driver will pick the customer up and drop him/her at the place mentioned. With the help of Smart phones, internet facility and GPS system the service is faster, easier, accurate, traceable and in fact economical when the customers are ready to share the taxi. Top ten mobile app based taxi/auto services in India are Ola cabs, Uber, Meru Cabs, Carzonrent, Savaari Car Rentals, Fastrack Taxi app, Mega cabs, Tab Cab, NTL Taxi and My Taxi India. The size of organised taxi market in India estimated for the year 2014 was \$500 million.

3. Mobile E-Wallet services

E-wallet is a type of pre-paid account in which a user can store his/her money for any future online transaction. An E-wallet is protected with a password. With the help of an E-wallet, one can make payments for groceries, online purchases, and flight tickets, among others.

E-wallet has mainly two components, software and information. The software component stores personal information and provides security and encryption of the data. The information component is a database of details provided by the user which includes their name, shipping address, payment method, amount to be paid, credit or debit card details, etc.

For setting up an E-wallet account, the user needs to install the software on his/her device, and enter the relevant information required. After shopping online, the E-wallet automatically fills in the user's information on the payment form. To activate the E-wallet, the user needs to enter his password. Once the online payment is made, the consumer is not required to fill the order form on any other website as the information gets stored in the database and is updated automatically. The most popular mobile e-wallets are PayTM, Momoe, PayUMoney, Mobikwik, Citrus, State bank buddy, Citi MasterPass, ICICI Pockets, HDFC Chillr, LIME, and Jio Money.

4. Real Estate Data base Apps

These are the mobile apps which facilitate the consumers to buy, sell or hire the properties for residential purposes. This service is initiated by the owners of the property. They post the details of the property along with the photographs of the property, its size, facilities available and price for which they want to sell or offer for hire. Later the people who want to buy or hire see the posts made by the owners and then the interested buyer and seller negotiate to finalise the deal. The greatest advantage to consumers is that this facility is provided by the companies without any cost or meager cost to consumers. The most famous mobile application in this category are MagicBricks, 99acres, Proptiger, Housing, Realtor, Commonfloor and The Wadhwa Group.

5. Pre-owned goods

People depended on friends, relatives, neighbours or local buyers/markets to sell their pre-owned or pre-used goods. But the advent of websites and mobile apps for selling pre-used items has enabled the sales of these items very quickly, easily and more profitably. The person who wants to sell the pre-used item make the post in the website or mobile apps with all necessary details which a buyer would want. Then the posts are viewed by the buyers to initiate the transaction. Wallapop, Quikr, Craigslist, Gumtree, Locanto, ebay classifieds, Yakaz and milanuncios are the prominent mobile applications in this category.

6. E-Buying Apps

E-buying application is one form of electronic commerce that allows consumers to directly buy goods and services from various sellers. Consumers who want to utilise this facility have to download and install the respective mobile application in their smart phones and create their own profile by giving necessary information. Then the consumers can view the products or services offered by the mobile application. The mobile applications provide all required information about the products and services in order to facilitate the consumers to take purchase decision. The consumers can either buy the products or services immediately or they can save the product in e-cart or favourite icon to buy in future. The consumers on selecting the items for purchase can either opt for pre-payment through online mode or they can opt for cash payment upon delivery. The mobile applications provide the facility for tracking their shipment delivery right after the order is placed. Then the ordered item will be delivered to the consumer at the place of consumers' choice which is mentioned by them at the time of ordering the items. Some e-shopping applications extend the facility of returning the product if the consumer is dissatisfied with the product which increases the credibility of e-shopping applications. The items which are marketed through the e-shopping applications are ranging from mobile phones to fashion, electronics home care, beauty care, toys&baby products, sports and many more. Amazon, Flipkart, eBay, Groupon, Grofers, H&M, paytm, walmart and wish are the famous applications in this category.

Conclusion

Mobile apps need to be both immersive and unique and contain features that will make shopping seamless and simpler. Make sure that you build your mobile app with features that will drive sales and give more revenue boost. Of course, an important thing to keep in mind, as with all business decisions, will the benefit of having the app out weigh the cost of building and maintaining the app. That all depend on your specific situation.

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